

Multi-sensor and multi-temporal mapping of the Roman city of *Pollentia* (Alcúdia, Mallorca): the ARCHREMOTELANDS project approach

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In recent years, technological advances in remote instruments such as RPAS or drone platforms, miniaturized sensors, GNSS positioning systems and photogrammetric software have certainly contributed to the consolidation of drone-based studies beyond experimental projects. Nowadays, this available technological toolkit is indispensable to archaeologists as shovels and trowels. Reliable remote sensing observations, however, are highly dependent on the accurate positioning of both the platform and the sensor employed, and a key challenge that remains seldom investigated is the integration (i.e. the co-registration) of newly acquired drone imagery with other geospatial datasets. These include multi-temporal drone orthomosaics from multiple flights (including multi-sensor imagery from distinct drone platforms and systems), as well as complementary aerial data (e.g. national orthophoto maps) and historical datasets such as topographical and geophysical legacy data.

This work summarises the ongoing drone-based research workflow being developed by the interdisciplinary team of ARCHREMOTELANDS (HAR2017-83335-P, University of Barcelona). The main aim of the project is to understand the evolution of the rural landscape in the hinterland of the Roman city of *Pollentia* (Alcúdia, north-western Mallorca). In particular, this contribution focus on 1) the generation and co-registration of multi-sensor and multi-source high-resolution drone orthomosaics and DEMs using public and freely available aerial data archives; 2) the automated delineation and vectorisation of visible archaeological remains from such orthophotos; and 3) the synergistic exploitation of multispectral and thermal bands to identify subsurface archaeological remains.

Our preliminary results show examples from the Roman city of *Pollentia*. We first examine how publicly available Spanish' *Plan Nacional de Ortofotografía Aérea* (PNOA) can be used to precisely identify GCPs and orthorectify multi-source and multi-temporal orthomosaics at subpixel resolution, thus reducing the need for alternative time and cost-consuming approaches such as topographical GCPs or precise drone GNSS-RTK positioning. Secondly, we discuss the possibilities of using open-source Orfeo ToolBox (OTB) libraries, including machine-learning methods, for the accurate classification of multi-band orthomosaics (i.e. VNIR and DEM bands). In particular, we have focused on the automated delineation of visible structural and architectural remains. Finally, we briefly outline the use of multispectral and thermal sensors to detect and map partially-buried features. This research workflow offers a set of open and freely available tools that can be used for effective and reliable documentation, site management and decision-making for future surveys and explorations, with an additional focus on data sharing and product dissemination to both scientific and non-expert audiences.